
Funding, Misappropriation, and Mismanagement as Predictors of Tertiary Education Management in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined how poor funding and misappropriation impacted tertiary education management in Nigeria. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study, the survey research design was adopted for the study, purposive sampling technique was used to select the tertiary institution and respondents for the study. A total of 109 senior management staff of the University of Calabar formed the population and sample for the study. The instrument for data collection was a 4-point response type scale developed by the researchers and titled "Effect of Poor Funding and Misappropriation Questionnaire (IPFMQ)". It was validated by experts in the department of Test and Measurement and Educational Management and pre-tested for reliability purposes with a good reliability estimate of .76 using Cronbach's alpha reliability. The results obtained revealed that poor funding, misappropriation and mismanagement of funds have a negative impact on the management of the tertiary institution, but misappropriation of funds have the most significant negative impact on tertiary education management in Nigeria. Based on these findings, a conclusion was drawn and recommendation that adequate funds should be made available for public institutions of tertiary education, while corruption and embezzlement should be reduced to the barest minimum. Premised on the findings of the study, it deduced that, funds sent for the management of high institutions are inadequate, and at the same time, misappropriation of such funds contributed more to poor management of the high institution. It was therefore recommended that competency issues should be taken seriously to ensure the appointment of tertiary institutional leaders and managers with requisite skills for prudent financial management and fund sourcing to complement government effort.

Keywords: Education, funding, management, misappropriation, tertiary.

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Introduction

Tertiary education in the 21st century is aimed at the achievement of a range of ends such as the development of knowledgeable and skilful individuals with the ability to think rationally, the formation of a sustainable community and the realization of economic goals benefiting both individuals and their communities. Both the Federal and State governments largely perceived

tertiary education as an investment in human capital development, intending to produce the required skilled manpower for managerial and technocratic levels of the economic, social and political sectors of the nation. More so, many secondary school leavers in Nigeria consider tertiary education as the only passport to self-fulfilment and a ladder to higher socio-economic status in society. Others are of the view that tertiary education is a formidable instrument that could be judiciously used in Nigeria to wipe out all social vices and economic woes such as corruption, bribery ignorance, conservatism, disease, malnutrition, tribalism, nepotism, political instability, unemployment and economic stagnation.

Educational management means the judicious utilization of available resources to achieve set goals. It includes all those techniques and procedures employed in operating the educational organizations following established practices. Afolabi (1998) defined educational management as "the identification, organization and coordination of human, material, physical and fiscal resources as well as other available education programmes, using them judiciously towards the attainment of objectives of education". From these definitions, educational management can be simply defined as the managerial process through which efforts of members of the educational system are coordinated, directed and guided towards the accomplishment of the goals of education, by carrying out management functions such as planning, organising, directing, financing, supervising, monitoring, inspecting and evaluating using the available limited resources.

Tertiary education management can be looked at from the internal and the external levels. At the internal level of management, each university is managed by a simple structure or organogram. The first is the Visitor who is usually the Head of State or the Head of Government that established it. The visitor is usually the President in the case of federal universities and the Governor in the case of state universities. He or she usually comes to grace key ceremonies organized like the convocation, where he uses the occasion to address the academic communities on matters of the moment (Adegbite, 2007). The second in the structure is the Chancellor, who is the titular head of the university, who by law, concerning the university, takes precedence before all other members of the university and when he is present, presides at all meetings of the convocation held for conferring degrees.

At the external level of university management, the federal government through the National Universities Commission (NUC) takes the lead. The body is charged with the coordination of university management in the country. According to Okojie (2007), the NUC activities in improving the quality of university education in the country includes the accreditation of courses, approval of courses and programmes, maintenance of minimum academic standards, monitoring of universities, giving guidelines for setting up of universities, etc. Besides, at the apex of the management structure within each university is the university Governing Council. This body is usually headed by the Pro-Chancellor, charged with administrative functions such as goal setting, policy formulation, staff development, general discipline, budget approval and liaison activities with the government. There is also the Senate, headed by the Vice-Chancellor and the Registrar as the Secretary. The Senate regulates the academic activities of the university following the general guidelines provided by the NUC.

Funding refers to a form of financial support that is given for the achievement of a project. Adequate funding of education guarantees staff development through academic programs like workshops, seminars, conferences, and scholarships. Most importantly, staff welfare and retention through regular payment of staff salaries and allowances are assured. It guarantees the protection of students welfare by providing playgrounds, refectories, lavatories, hostels, resource centres, etc.; and the maintenance of a healthy schooling environment via a good sanitary environment, avert multiple disciplinary problems, regular maintenance, etc. (Agabi, 2014; Ololube, 2016). Public expenditure is seen to be the responsibility of the government's social services and responsibilities of which the funding of education is one. In furtherance of this, section 13(120) of the National Policy on Education (NPE) recognized that education is an expensive social service that requires adequate financial provision from all tiers of government for successful implementation of educational programs, (Federal Republic of Nigeria FRN, 2004).

Adequate funding of education at all levels determines the quality of the educational system that is functional in any nation. This is because funds are the life wire of these institutions. After all, monies provide the purchasing power of the institutions to provide physical materials needed in these institutions, and adequate funds determine the hiring capabilities of staff of tertiary education institutions. Therefore, it is believed that with well-funded education programs in place, nations are guaranteed effective and first-class brains that will propel national and regional development. Undoubtedly, tertiary education in Nigeria today could be seen as a reliable instrument that assists the nation in meeting her social, political, moral, cultural, technological and economic aspirations, by inculcating in the individual knowledge, skills, dexterity, commendable demeanour and desirable attitudes and values that foster national development. For the Nigerian tertiary educational institutions to accomplish the lofty goal of producing the required manpower skills that will contribute meaningfully to national growth and development, greater attention must be given to quality control, sound management, monitoring and supervision of the tertiary educational institutions. This is unfortunately not the case due to the many challenges confronting the management of tertiary education. It is worrisome to note that tertiary institutions in the country are fast decaying due to management crises largely caused by poor funding. All the resources required for the education production process are in short supply. Lecture halls, laboratories, students' hostels, library space, books and journals and office spaces are all seriously inadequate (Ochuba, 2001).

Akindutire (2004) stated that institutional deterioration and salary erosion during the past decade have prompted substantial "brain-drain" of academic staff and impeded new staff recruitment. Most devastating is the long-standing problem of graduate unemployment. According to Akindutire (2004), the problem of graduate unemployment is a reality in Nigeria where graduates had to wait for upwards of five years to get a job in the public service. Other problems in the management of the university system in Nigeria include the rising demand for admission and the cost of university education, frequent cases of sexual harassment, examination malpractices (Odia & Omofonmwan, 2007; Mgbekem, 2007). Volatile and

militant student unionism, political interference and cultism are among the challenges that educational managers are faced with.

Another serious challenge facing the management of tertiary institutions in Nigeria today is how to handle the menace and aggressiveness of cult members. The destruction of lives and property on campuses has been so great now than it was before (Ogunbameru, 2004). In the same vein, Adegbite (2007) remarked that the issue of cultism among the students has opened a new and very dangerous dimension to the situation of things in our educational institutions. Smah (2007) posited that where cults exist, there is no guarantee that academic programmes and activities would run normally. Hence the university may run the risk of being constantly closed or disrupted. Unfortunately, it appears that managers of tertiary education are not living up to expectations in carrying out their statutory responsibilities in the areas of funds management, funds appropriation, protection of lives and properties of the staff. All the resources needed for the education production process are in short supply such as hostels, library space, lecture halls, laboratories, students' books and journals. Notwithstanding several interventions by the government and other agencies at ensuring quality education for its citizenry, university education still suffers from poor educational facilities and services. Insecurity has crept into the education system. Kidnapping and abduction is now a big business for the bad guys. Pupils, students, teachers and lecturers are not spared.

Literature and concerned stakeholders in education have blamed the poor management of tertiary education in Nigeria on inadequate funding and misappropriation of resources. This was seen from the views of Oyeneye (2006) and Adegbite (2007) who stated that the major challenge facing the management of the university system in Nigeria is inadequate funding. The shortage of funds available to the university system has been responsible for declining teaching, social and laboratory facilities in Nigerian universities in recent years and has made the governance of the university system a hard task. According to Okebukola (2002); Marinho (2002); Ekankumo and Kemebaradikumo (2014), poor funding and the misappropriation of funds within the educational system has led to the dysfunctional and unethical practices that have generated limitations across Nigeria's educational system, especially in tertiary education. They further assert that poor funding and inadequate implementation of budgetary allocations has led to incidences of backlogs of results, late preparation of results, insufficient staffing, non-availability of most important instructional materials, etc.

Misappropriation is an intentional or illegal use of funds for one's use or other unauthorized purposes, particularly by public officials (Mestry, 2004). Such an act is an unauthorized disbursement of money or other assets for personal gain. Misappropriation of funds is the highest type of fraud committed in all sectors of the economy. People deliberately convert the public fund to personal use without a blink of fear or conscience disturbance. Misappropriation is committed by outright taking away of corporate or government assets for personal use, payment for fictitious purchase and contract, cutting costs and manipulating financial records for personal needs, embezzlement, etc. Therefore, poor funding, misappropriation and mismanagement can negatively impact tertiary education management in Nigeria. Realizing this, the government and some concerned stakeholders have over the years

done their best to remedy the situation by providing funding for tertiary education management yet the effort seems to be rather grossly inadequate considering the phenomenal increase in student enrolment and increasing cost of governance. It is against this background that this study sought to investigate the impact of poor funding and misappropriation on tertiary education management in Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

Poor funding of tertiary education has created loopholes in the management of Nigeria tertiary education in terms of provision of resilient infrastructure, purchase of instructional materials, staff and student's welfare. The unauthorized, misappropriation, intentional or illegal use of the appropriated funds for tertiary education by institutional leaders for other unauthorized purposes have a negative effect on proper and effective management, planning and control of the quality management of tertiary education in Nigeria. This has put the universities in very bad shape causing the teaching staff to hunt for greener pastures abroad. The mismanagement of funds meant for Nigerian institutions of tertiary learning has thrown Nigeria in a bad light. The little funds appropriated to these institutions are grossly mismanaged and this has caused the quality of tertiary education to rather deteriorate. Misappropriation and mismanagement of funds have put the university management under immense stress and strains hence they are incapacitated in providing essential services. This has led to rampant crises in the system resulting in strike actions by academic and non-academic staff, dearth of equipment and facilities, indiscipline among staff and students, upsurge in the activities of secret cults, sexual harassment, graduate unemployment, erosion of university autonomy, and most saddening of frustration due to poor incentives and lack of motivation to engage in meaningful researches.

Today public tertiary institutions struggle to provide adequate hostels, library space, lecture halls and laboratories. Many academic staff do not have office space to carry out their duties and so have to either squat with their colleagues or operate from under trees and parked vehicles or their homes. The present situation has raised concerns as to whether tertiary education in Nigeria will be able to attain the goal of national development through high-level relevant manpower training. Given this state of affairs, this study is aimed at investigating the impact of poor funding and appropriation on tertiary education management in Nigeria.

Funding

Adequate funding of education guarantees staff welfare and retention through regular payment of staff salaries and allowances assured as well as staff development through academic programs like workshops, seminars, conferences, and scholarships. Expenditure on education is seen as one of the major responsibilities of government. According to Okebukola (2002); Marinho (2002); Ekankumo and Kemebaradikumo (2014), poor funding and the misappropriation of funds within the educational system has led to the dysfunctional and unethical practices that have generated limitations across Nigeria's educational system, especially in tertiary education. They further assert that poor funding and inadequate implementation of budgetary allocations has led to incidences of a backlog of results, late

preparation of results, insufficient staffing, non-availability of most important instructional materials, etc.

Some studies (e.g., Ekaette, Owan and Agbo, 2019; Odigwe & Owan (2019) discovered that the inadequate funding of tertiary education by the Nigeria government has contributed immensely to the decay in the sector, especially since the country is unable to meet the recommended UNESCO's benchmark of 26 per cent of every developing country's annual budget to be invested on funding education. However, regardless of the annual budgetary provisions by the Nigerian governments over the years, the standard of education in the country has continued to decrease because tertiary education leaders are not sincere as monies meant for tertiary education is often used for other purposes. Asiyai (2015) conducted a study to investigate strategies for effective management of tertiary education for building a culture of peace in Nigeria. The findings revealed that curricula related, life skills related, institutional climate-related and funding related were strategies for effective management of education for building a culture of peace in Nigeria.

Misappropriation of funds

Misappropriation is an intentional or illegal use of funds for one's use or other unauthorized purposes, particularly by public officials (Mestry, 2004). Such an act is an unauthorized disbursement of money or other assets for personal gain. Misappropriation of funds is the highest type of fraud committed in all sectors of the economy. People deliberately convert public funds to personal use without a blink of fear or conscience disturbance. Misappropriation is committed by outright taking away of corporate or government assets for personal use, payment for fictitious purchase and contract, cutting costs and manipulating financial records for personal needs, embezzlement, Etc. Erhieyovwe and Andrew (2019) conducted a study to evaluate the effect of tertiary institution funding on national development in Nigeria. An ordinary least squares estimation technique was used in the study to evaluate the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The result of the experiment indicates that funding is a veritable tool for tertiary institutions growth in Nigeria. The result also shows that government capital expenditure funding is not statistically significant in the growth process. According to Ololube and Aiya (2016), if higher education institutions are adequately funded, it creates room for better infrastructural development and maintenance of school buildings, office blocks, classroom blocks, student hostels, staff quarters, etc.

Mismanagement of funds

Mismanagement is an intentional misuse of money. According to Chikowore in Mapolisa, Ncube, Tshabalala and Khosa (2014) stated that the number of cases of embezzlement and mismanagement of funds by higher education leaderships in Nigerian is quite frightening. Funds mismanagement cases have serious economic effects on the organization. It may result in the loss of funds and assets of the organization. The loss of liquid assets will further lead to the reduction of revenue for current and capital expenditures, with the attendant reduction in the level of economic operations, reduction in revenue inflow and provision of socio-economic

infrastructure for the public. Similarly, the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), reported that out of the 701 development projects in Nigeria universities, 163(23.3%) are abandoned, and 538(76.7%) are perpetually under ongoing projects. Some of the abandoned projects in Nigerian universities are over fifteen years old and some are over forty years old. 76% of Nigerian universities use well as a source of water, 45% use pit latrines and 67% of students use the bush as toilets. Governments are interested in expending money on the creation of new universities, instead of consolidating and expanding access to existing ones; they are keen to award new contracts rather than complete the abandoned projects or standardize existing facilities (ASUU, 2016).

Summary of literature review

Effective management of tertiary education is largely dependent on adequate funding and its prudent appropriation. With well-funded education programs in place, nations are guaranteed effective and first-class brains that will propel national and regional development. Related literature so far reviewed in this study revealed that poor funding and appropriation has put the university management under immense stress and strains hence they are incapacitated in providing essential services. The situation has led to rampant crises in the system resulting in strikes by academic and non-academic staff, dearth of equipment and facilities amongst others. The effort of the government and some concerned stakeholders at funding has been considered to be rather grossly inadequate considering the phenomenal increase in student enrolment and increasing grossly inadequate cost of governance. The government is still unable to meet the recommended UNESCO's benchmark of 26 per cent of every developing country's annual budget to be invested in funding education. The review of literature so far indicated there were few studies carried out on funding and tertiary education management in Nigeria. Thus, this study sought to fill the gap.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to assess the impact of poor funding and misappropriation of the fund on tertiary educational management in Nigeria. This study specifically sought to achieve the following three objectives:

1. To evaluate the impact of poor funding on the management of the tertiary institutions.
2. To evaluate the impact of misappropriation of funds on the management of tertiary institutions
3. To evaluate the impact of mismanagement of funds on the management of tertiary institutions.
4. To determine the cumulative impact of funding, misappropriation and mismanagement of funds on the management of tertiary institutions.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to direct the study

1. There is no significant impact of funding on the management of tertiary institutions.
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2. There is no significant impact of misappropriation of funds on the management of tertiary institutions.
3. There is no significant impact of mismanagement of funds on the management of tertiary institutions.
4. There is no significant impact of funding, misappropriation of funds and the mismanagement of funds on the management of tertiary institutions.

Methods

This study is a survey research design carried out in one tertiary institution in Cross Rivers State, Nigeria (University of Calabar). The population of the study was faculty of education and social science members and senior management staff of the University of Calabar in Cross Rivers State, Nigeria. In this study, the respondents comprised 67 academic staff and 42 non-academic staff in two faculties (Education and Social Science). A purposive sample procedure was adopted to select a sample for the study. All the respondents agreed to participate in the study after reading the first page of the questionnaire which presented a detailed view of the purpose of the study. A 100% response rate was achieved.

The data for the study were collected by two research assistants. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire developed by the researchers and titled “Effect of Poor Funding and Misappropriation Questionnaire (EPFMQ)”. The questionnaire was designed and validated by specialists in measurement and evaluation. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents in their offices. The questionnaire comprised four sections. Section 1 contained information on respondents' demographic variables and included items like age, gender, academic staff, and non-academic staff for respondents' demographic variables. Section 2 presented issues of education funding in Nigeria. The section highlighted variables of education funding in Nigeria that are presumed to serve as the basis for the management of tertiary education. The section comprised of 10 items and was structured along a 4-Point Likert scale of 1=substantially inadequate, 2=inadequate, 3=adequate, and 4=substantially adequate. Section 3 of the questionnaire evaluated staff perception of funds misappropriation in tertiary education. It consisted of variables of education funds misappropriation in Nigeria and comprised of 11 items. It was structured along 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=agree, and 4=strongly agree.

Section 4 recounts variables on education funds mismanagement in Nigerian tertiary education. The section was designed to examine academic and non-academic staff perceptions of the influence of funds mismanagement and how it impacts the management of tertiary education. It comprised 10 items. The overall Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis was .765. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 was employed and descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), linear regression analysis was conducted to determine the impact of the independent variables (funding, misappropriation of fund and mismanagement of fund) on the dependent variable (management of tertiary education).

Results

The composite impact of funding, misappropriation of funds and mismanagement of funds on the management of tertiary institutions as reflected in the hypothesis were ascertain using multiple regression statistical analysis. The hypothesis was tested at the .05 level of significance. Table 1 presents the result of the findings. The model summary of the regression analysis conducted (Table 1) showed significant relationships between funding, misappropriation of funds and mismanagement of funds on tertiary education management in Nigeria using R of .781^a, R square of .609 and an Adjusted R Square of .605 of the complete variables entered. Therefore, the value of R² showed that 60.9% of the variables that accounts for the management of tertiary education in Nigeria are a result of inadequate funding, misappropriation and mismanagement of education funds. What this represents is that the remaining 39.1% in the variation of management of tertiary education in Nigeria could be caused by several other variables.

The ANOVA analysis presented the sum of squares for the regression to be 85.803 and that of the residual to be 55.008, and a degree of freedom of 3 and 105. The mean square for the regression is displayed as 28.601 and a residual of .202, with an F-value of 141.423 and a p-value of .000^b. The observed p-value was less than the acceptable p-value of .05, with this, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant impact of funding, misappropriation of funds and mismanagement of funds on the management of tertiary institutions was rejected. This implies that funding, misappropriation and mismanagement have a significant impact on the management of tertiary education in Nigeria.

Table 1: Multiple regression statistical analysis of the impact of funding, misappropriation of funds, and mismanagement of funds on the management of tertiary institutions.

Model summary					
R	R2	Ad. R2	SE		
.781 ^a	.609	.605	.445		
ANOVA					
Source	SS	DF	MS	F	p
Regression	85.803	2	28.601	141.423	.000
Residual	55.008	108	106		
Total	140.812				
Relative Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardised Coefficients		
	B	SE	Beta	t	p
Constant	1.450	.186		7.779	.000
Funding	.221	.047	.214	4.700	.000
Misappropriation	.700	.041	.705	17.187	.000
Mismanagement	-.361	.051	-.305	-7.110	.000

a). Dependent Variable: Tertiary Education management.

b). Predictors: (Constant), Education Funds, Misappropriation

The regression model in Table can be expressed in linear equation form as;
 $MTE = 1.450 + .22 (F) + .700 (MISAF) - .361 (MISMF)$ 1

Where:

MTE = Management of Tertiary Education

F = Funding

MISAF = Misappropriation of Funds

MISMF = Mismanagement of Funds

Discussion

On funding of the tertiary institution in Nigeria, the observed p-value was significant at .05 with the calculated t-value of 4.700. The null hypothesis was rejected because the p-value was less than .05. This implies that funding of higher institutions has a significant impact on the management of tertiary education programs in Nigeria. The finding in this study was in line with that of Okebukola (2002), Marinho (2002) and Ekankumo and Kemebaradikumo (2014), that poor funding and the misappropriation of funds within the educational system has led to the dysfunctional and unethical practices that have generated limitations across Nigeria's educational system, especially in tertiary education. They further assert that poor funding and inadequate implementation of budgetary allocations has led to incidences of a backlog of results, late preparation of results, insufficient staffing, non-availability of most important instructional materials, etc.

Misappropriation of education funds also accounts for the management of tertiary education in Nigeria. This is depicted in the coefficient table with a significant level of .00 and the calculated t-value of 17.187. What this means is that misappropriation of tertiary education funds has a significant negative impact on the management of tertiary education. Thus, hypothesis 2 which stated that —there is no significant impact of misappropriation of funds on the management of tertiary education in Nigeria was rejected. The findings in this study agree with that of Mestry (2004) that misappropriation is an intentional or illegal use of funds for one's use and other unauthorized purposes, particularly by public officials. Similarly, Erhieyovwe and Andrew, (2019) conducted a study to evaluate the effect of tertiary institutions' funding on national development in Nigeria. An ordinary least squares estimation technique was used in the study to evaluate the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The result of the experiment indicates that funding is a veritable tool for tertiary institutions growth in Nigeria. The result also shows that government capital expenditure funding is not statistically significant in the growth process. According to Ololube and Aiya (2016), if higher education institutions are adequately funded, it creates room for better infrastructural development and maintenance of school buildings, office blocks, classroom blocks, student hostels, staff quarters, etc.

Mismanagement of education funds equally accounts for the management of tertiary education in Nigeria. A significance level of .00 was seen from the coefficient table which was

less than .05 with a calculated t-value of -7.110. Thus, hypothesis 3 which stated that —there is no significant impact of mismanagement of funds on the management of tertiary education in Nigeria was rejected. The implication is that mismanagement of funds has a significant negative impact on the management of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. This study's finding agrees with that of Chikowore in Mapolisa, Ncube, Tshabalala and Khosa (2014) that the number of cases of embezzlement and mismanagement of funds by higher education leaderships in Nigerian is quite frightening. Funds mismanagement cases have serious economic effects on the organization. It may result in the loss of funds and assets of the organization. The loss of liquid assets will further lead to the reduction of revenue for current and capital expenditures, with the attendant reduction in the level of economic operations, reduction in revenue inflow and provision of socio-economic infrastructure for the public.

Similarly, the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), reported that out of the 701 development projects in Nigeria universities, 163(23.3%) are abandoned, and 538(76.7%) are perpetually under ongoing projects. Some of the abandoned projects in Nigerian universities are over fifteen years old and some are over forty years old. 76% of Nigerian universities use well as a source of water, 45% use pit latrines and 67% of students use the bush as toilets. Governments are interested in expending money on the creation of new universities, instead of consolidating and expanding access to existing ones; they are keen to award new contracts rather than complete the abandoned projects or standardize existing facilities (ASUU, 2016). The regression coefficient table further revealed that the strongest contributor to the overall coefficient is the misappropriation of funds with the beta weight of .705 ($\beta = .705$) followed by funding ($\beta = .214$) and finally mismanagement of fund ($\beta = -.305$). It may be deduced that funds sent for the management of higher institutions are inadequate, and at the same time, misappropriation of such funds contributed more to management of the higher institutions.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to examine the impact of funding, misappropriation and mismanagement of funds on the management of tertiary institutions in Nigerian. The investigation revealed that the funding of tertiary education has created loopholes in the management of Nigeria's tertiary education in terms of provision of resilient infrastructure, purchase of instructional materials, staff and student's welfare. The unauthorized, misappropriation, intentional or illegal use of the appropriated funds for tertiary education by institutional leaders for other unauthorized purposes have a negative effect on proper and effective management, planning and control of the quality management of tertiary education in Nigeria. The mismanagement of funds meant for Nigerian institutions of tertiary learning has thrown Nigeria in a bad light. The little funds appropriated to these institutions are grossly mismanaged. Since Nigerian institutional leaders mismanage their funds, the quality of tertiary education is bound to deteriorate.

Recommendations

Arising from the results of the findings, it was recommended that competency issues should be taken seriously to ensure the appointment of tertiary institutional leaders with requisite skills for prudent financial management and fund sourcing to complement government effort.

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